

1 **Supplementary figures**

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4 **Figure S1. Effect of different MOI of RV-A16 and RV-A1B on mRNA expression of**
5 ***IL33* in primary bronchial epithelial cells (S-PBEC).** S-PBEC (n = 1-5 donor mixes; 4-
6 5 different donors/mix) were first refreshed with hydrocortisone-free medium for
7 24 h and subsequently infected with mock or with different MOI RV-A16 or RV-
8 A1B for 48 h. Expression of *IL33* mRNA was determined by qPCR. Normalized gene
9 expression was calculated by using the expression of tyrosine 3-
10 monooxygenase/tryptophan 5-monooxygenase activation protein zeta (*YWHAZ*)
11 and ribosomal protein L27 (*RPL27*) as reference genes. Next, fold changes in gene
12 expression compared to CNTRL were calculated and data are shown as individual
13 values, and as means \pm SEM.

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17 **Figure S2. Effect of FD on papain-mediated protein release of IL-33 in submerged**
 18 **cultures of primary bronchial epithelial cells (S-PBEC).** S-PBEC (4 donor mixes of
 19 4-5 different donors) were first preincubated with 200 µg/mL farm dust extract
 20 (FD) for 24 h and subsequently stimulated with 20 ng/mL TNF-α/30 ng/mL IFN-γ
 21 with or without TNF-α for 7 h to increase cellular protein expression of IL-33,
 22 followed by addition of 30 µg/mL papain (Merck Life Science NV) for 30 min to
 23 provoke an active release of IL-33 in the supernatant. IL-33 protein levels in S-
 24 PBEC supernatant were measured by using HEK-Blue™ IL-33 reporter cells. To
 25 determine IL-33 protein levels, HEK-Blue™ IL-33 reporter cells were seeded in a
 26 96-well plate and incubated with the conditioned medium of the stimulated S-
 27 PBEC for 24 h. IL-33 induced SEAP levels in the HEK-Blue™ IL-33 reporter cell
 28 supernatant was measured using a spectrophotometer at O.D. 650 nm. Data are
 29 presented as means ± SEM. Data were analyzed using a two-way ANOVA and
 30 Dunnett's post-hoc test. * p < 0.05, ** p < 0.01.
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34 **Figure S3. Effect of TNF-α on IFN-γ-mediated mRNA and protein expression of IL-**
 35 **33 in differentiated primary bronchial epithelial cells (ALI-PBEC).** ALI-PBEC
 36 (donor mix of 5 different donors) were stimulated with IFN-γ with or without TNF-
 37 α for 4 h to determine mRNA expression of *IL33* by qPCR and for 8 h to assess IL-
 38 33 protein levels by using HEK-Blue™ IL-33 reporter cells. Normalized gene
 39 expression was calculated by using the expression of tyrosine 3-
 40 monooxygenase/tryptophan 5-monooxygenase activation protein zeta (*YWHAZ*)
 41 and ribosomal protein L27 (*RPL27*) as reference genes. To determine IL-33 protein
 42 levels, 300 μL HEK-Blue™ medium was added at the apical side of the stimulated
 43 cells, followed by 3 × freeze-thaw cycles to provoke cellular damage and release
 44 of IL-33 in the medium. Next, HEK-Blue™ IL-33 reporter cells were seeded in a 96-
 45 well plate and incubated with the conditioned medium of the stimulated ALI-PBEC
 46 for 24 h. IL-33 induced SEAP levels in the HEK-Blue™ IL-33 reporter cell
 47 supernatant was measured using a spectrophotometer at O.D. 650 nm. To
 48 calculate intracellular IL-33 levels, a standard curve of recombinant human IL-33
 49 (16-0.25 ng/mL) was used to determine the IL-33 concentration in the ALI-PBEC.
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Figure S4. Effect of inhibitors on LDH-release and on phosphorylated (p)-p38 and P-EGFR in INF-γ-stimulated submerged cultures of primary bronchial epithelial cells (S-PBEC). S-PBEC (n = 3 donor mixes) were first preincubated with inhibitors of downstream IFN-γ-signaling pathways (JAK, p38 MAPK, EGFR and NF-κB) or with 200 μg/mL farm dust extract (FD) and subsequently stimulated with 30 ng/mL IFN-γ for 30 min to assess phosphorylated (p)-p38 and p-EGFR by western blot analysis or for 6 h to determine LDH release. (A) LDH release is presented as fold change compared to CNTRL-treated samples. (B) To assess effects on p-p38 and p-EGFR, densitometry was used and ratios between p-p38 and p-EGFR and the reference protein GAPDH were calculated. Data are presented as means of fold change (compared to control stimulated S-PBEC) ± SEM. Data were analyzed using a two-way ANOVA and Dunnett’s post-hoc test. ** p < 0.01, *** p < 0.001.

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Figure S5. Effect of Pam3CSK on TNF- α /IFN- γ -mediated mRNA expression of IL-33 in primary bronchial epithelial cells (S-PBEC). S-PBEC (donor mix of 4 different donors) were first preincubated with 200 μ g/mL (S-PBEC) or with 1-5 μ g/mL Pam3CSK (Invivogen) for 24 h and stimulated with 20 ng/mL TNF- α and 30 ng/mL IFN- γ for 6 h to determine mRNA expression of *IL33* by qPCR. Normalized gene expression was calculated by using the expression of tyrosine 3-monooxygenase/tryptophan 5-monooxygenase activation protein zeta (*YWHAZ*) and ribosomal protein L27 (*RPL27*) as reference genes. Next, fold changes in gene expression compared to CNTRL were calculated and data are shown as individual values.

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Figure S6. Effect of FD on IL-8 and CXCL-10 release in submerged cultures of primary bronchial epithelial cells (S-PBEC). S-PBEC ($n = 5$ donors) were first preincubated with 200 μ g/mL farm dust extract (FD) for 24 h and subsequently stimulated with 20 ng/mL TNF- α /30 ng/mL IFN- γ or with 50 ng/mL IL-4/5 μ g/mL Poly(I:C) in presence or absence of FD for 6 h and 24 h to assess IL-8 release and for 24 h to assess CXCL-10 release by using an ELISA. Data are presented as means \pm SEM. Data were analyzed using a two-way ANOVA and Dunnett's post-hoc test. * $p < 0.05$.

91 **References**

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